

TOPICAL REVIEW

Vessel Trajectory Data Mining: A Review

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ABSTRACT Recent advancements in sensor and tracking technologies have facilitated the real-time tracking of marine vessels as they traverse the oceans. As a result, there is an increasing demand to analyze these datasets to derive insights into vessel movement patterns and to investigate activities occurring within specific spatial and temporal contexts. This survey offers a comprehensive review of contemporary research in trajectory data mining, with a particular focus on maritime applications. The article collects and evaluates state-of-the-art algorithmic approaches and key techniques pertinent to various use case scenarios within this domain. Furthermore, this study provides an in-depth analysis of recent developments in trajectory data mining as applied to the maritime sector, identifying available data sources and conducting a detailed examination of significant applications, including trajectory forecasting, activity recognition, and trajectory clustering.

INDEX TERMS Maritime monitoring, data mining, spatio-temporal data mining, trajectory analytics, pattern mining, descriptive analytics, predictive analytics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The large amounts of data produced on a daily basis, due to the digitization of most industries, create both opportunities and challenges for their exploitation [1], [2]. Besides collecting and storing these datasets, the extraction of useful information has also been the focus of dedicated studies, especially during the past two decades of the big data boom [3]. The process of uncovering underlying patterns and extracting hidden relationships in the collected data is called data mining (DM). Related DM tasks are concerned with the grouping of the records, their assignment to a specific class, automatic summarization, prediction of future entries and others [4]. Depending on the features that are included in the processed data records, specific categories of DM can be defined. The study of data that have both a spatial and a temporal dimension, in order to extract useful insights and patterns, is called spatio-temporal DM [5]. In turn, the

subcategory of analysis on records that describe the behavior of moving objects is referred to as mobility DM [6].

Focusing on the maritime domain, and more specifically vessel trajectories, analytics on mobility data can be quite useful for several end-users of the shipping industry [7], allowing for the development of Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) [8], [9]. ITS can help optimize port logistics [10] and manage the environmental impact of shipping activities [11], [12], helping environmental organizations and researchers to advocate for sustainable practices. The decision-making process of vessel operators while underway can also highly benefit from automatically interpreting the behavior and intentions of other nearby vessels, towards safer navigation. During route planning, captains as well as fleet managers, may incorporate shipping trends in their process of determining optimized routes for their vessels. At the same time, insurance companies assess risk and determine premiums based on vessel behavior. Moreover, port authorities and law enforcement agencies use maritime mobility analytics to monitor human activity at sea, ensure

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compliance with safety and environmental regulations and identify instances of illegal activities or life endangerment (such as smuggling and unauthorized fishing). Finally, with the recent rise of autonomous vessel technologies, situational awareness is paramount to enable their safe operation in real-world conditions [13], [14].

Several systems responsible for the constant tracking of the vessel movement, have been employed over the years [15], generating frequent positional reports, for the global fleet of more than 200,000 ships. Besides their positions, vessel-related attributes like their type or dimensions are also available. Since these monitoring systems have been operational for more than 15 years, advanced DM techniques on the resulting large datasets allow for extracting useful insights for the study of human activities at sea. However, the complexity of data analysis, the need for advanced analytical tools, and the integration of diverse datasets pose significant challenges for these stakeholders in effectively utilizing such datasets. Furthermore, the plethora of academic approaches to trajectory analysis can create confusion and inconsistency in methodologies, making it difficult for practitioners to apply findings in a practical context.

The multitude of methods for the several DM tasks related to spatio-temporal and mobility data has been described in numerous dedicated reviews [16], [17], [18]. A noteworthy example of such a study can be found in the work by Zheng in [19], where the different steps of processing trajectory records are presented in great detail. Together with the major DM tasks found in mobility data, this work delineates the transformation of such data into several formats and provides a list of some open dataset for experimentation. Furthermore, Atluri et al. in [5] provide an review for the several types of spatio-temporal data and the respective methods for the different DM tasks. Other studies are set out to tackle a single task, like trajectory clustering [20], classification [21] and location prediction [22]. The growing interest for deep learning architectures extends to the domain of spatio-temporal data processing [23]. More precisely, Graser et al. in [24] (following their shorter review in [25]) describe the trends and implementations that use deep learning in processing mobility data. The fact that this full study was conducted solely on works after 2018 highlights the increasing popularity of such approaches in processing mobility data. Comprehensive examinations of the challenges and open problems for future works on spatio-temporal data can be found in [26] and [27], with the latter focusing solely on mobility datasets. These works have been much broader in focus, lacking direct applicability to the maritime domain, which further limits their usefulness for stakeholders seeking specific insights related to vessel movement and behavior.

Beyond these general studies on spatio-temporal data analysis, several works that focus on specific problems related to maritime mobility have been published. In particular, the work by Riviero et al. in [28] indicated a significant increase on articles regarding anomaly detection upon vessel tracks.

More recent reviews for detection methods on anomalies regarding the vessel's movement (speed, course and/or position) and traffic can be found in [29], [30], and [31]. Similarly, predicting vessel behavior has been the subject for a few systematic studies [32], [33], [34], [35]. Artificial intelligence techniques, and especially deep learning, has proven to be the most prominent category of approaches since the year 2020 [32]. An experimental comparison for different machine learning implementations on vessel route forecasting was presented by Chondrodima et al. in [36], while a similar examination of the methods for predicting traffic flow can be found in [37]. Other tasks with dedicated studies include collision avoidance [38], mapping fishing activities [39], trajectory compression [40], [41] and weather routing [42]. Even though these works are of very high quality, they describe the state-of-the-art for selected use case scenarios and do not provide an overview of the vessel mobility DM approaches available.

There exist few previous survey studies that have attempted to address this gap in analytics on vessel trajectory data. Most notably, the work by Xiao et al. in [43] provides a technical overview of the different approaches for both analyzing vessel traffic and providing effective forecasts for the future. The study discusses the extraction of frequent patterns from vessel traffic data, through graph, vector and statistical analyses, and presents the different strategies to tackle forecasting of future vessel behavior. The use of learning-based techniques for predictive analysis of vessel trajectories is discussed in length, from support vector machines and associative learning to neural networks approaches and Markov Chain methods. Another extensive study on vessel mobility data analytics was presented by Tu et al. in [44]. This work is concerned with exploiting data from a specific source of information, namely the Automatic Identification System (AIS), presenting the possible data mining tasks that can be solved (anomaly detection, collision risk assessment, route forecasting and path planning). The different application scenarios of AIS data, including cases of trade analysis, emissions reduction and ship performance evaluation, were described in [45] and in an analysis more focused on the nature of the data in [46]. Alternative usages for the AIS network, like transmitting weather-related measurements and observations, are discussed in [47]. However, these works have rapidly become outdated mostly due to the exponential growth of big data and advancements in technology. The increasing volume, velocity, and variety of maritime data challenge the relevance and applicability of earlier methodologies, necessitating continuous updates and innovations in analytical approaches to keep pace with the evolving landscape of maritime activities. A recent work that discusses multiple DM applications for the maritime industry and touches on possible directions for the future, including the generation of a model similar to Large Language Models, was presented in [48]. Likewise, a taxonomy for visual analytics on vessel trajectories was presented in [49], tackling

problems from density maps generation to behavior pattern analysis. Nevertheless, these overview articles present the different problems found in vessel trajectory data and then deal only with solutions using machine learning and visual analytics respectively, without being concerned with possible alternatives found in the literature. Two overview articles were presented in 2021 by Jin et al. [50] and by Newaliya and Singh [51], providing solid introductions on the major concepts regarding maritime data analytics. In this work, we provide a detailed and technical breakdown of data mining tasks for vessel trajectories, together with the respective state-of-the-art approaches.

In summary, the novelty of this survey paper emerges from the imperative to collect and analyze approaches that effectively address the challenges associated with large-scale data management and those incorporating innovative artificial intelligence methodologies, that have surfaced in recent years. This necessity arises from the recognition that many traditional methods have become ineffective in light of these advancements. Furthermore, the paper is comprehensive in scope, encompassing a wide array of needs and strategies pertinent to specific use cases, with a particular emphasis on the maritime domain, thereby ensuring that the discussed approaches are directly applicable and beneficial to this critical field.

In this study we provide a review for data mining upon vessel trajectories, expanding our brief overview work in [52]. The contributions of this study are:

- 1) we provide a brief introduction on big data mining, and the processing of spatio-temporal datasets.
- 2) we describe the domain of vessel mobility data, listing possible interested end-users and the major categories of data sources.
- 3) we give an overview of the most crucial steps for preparing such datasets, including filtering and reconstruction.
- 4) we present the major DM tasks for both descriptive and predictive analytics on vessel trajectories (see Figure 1).
- 5) we mention prominent and indicative state-of-the-art works that address each of the aforementioned tasks.
- 6) we list some of the most important challenges for vessel trajectory data mining, indicating possible directions regarding future works.

A lot of the published works for maritime trajectory processing fall in more than one type of DM tasks. For example, a method that extracts frequent mobility patterns in an area can frequently be used to determine predictions of a vessel's future behavior or anomaly detection. For this study we consider each work's intended scope in determining its category. Since we only focus on trajectory data processing, we do not include vessel detection techniques from remote sensing images or cameras [53], [54], [55].

The study is organized as follows. The first part of this paper provides a broad overview on big data processing

FIGURE 1. Categorizing different works on vessel trajectory DM based on their goal. The input dataset should be prepared for further analysis, through filtering invalid and irrelevant records and by reconstructing incomplete trajectories. Moreover, descriptive analytics on vessel trajectories allow for the extraction of routes of common movement, the detection of abnormal behavior and specific activity recognition (such as fishing). Finally, predictive analytics provide forecasts regarding the path the vessel will follow, its intended destination and the estimated time of arrival, while incorporating the weather conditions can produce more informed recommendations for its upcoming behavior.

and spatio-temporal data mining, highlighting key concepts, methodologies, and applications (Section II). In contrast, the second part specifically focuses on the maritime domain, delving into the unique challenges and opportunities associated with analyzing vessel trajectory data. This dual approach aims to contextualize maritime analytics within the larger framework of spatio-temporal studies while addressing the specific needs and insights pertinent to maritime stakeholders. We give an overview of vessel trajectory data, describing the available data sources (Section III) and the required steps for preparing such datasets (Section IV). We proceed on presenting the most prominent DM tasks, along with the most important works, for both descriptive and predictive analytics on vessel trajectories (Sections V and VI respectively). Finally, we discuss the challenges found in vessel trajectory DM and potential directions for future works (Section VII) and provide our concluding remarks (Section VIII).

II. BIG SPATIO-TEMPORAL DATA MINING

During the past two decades, the digitalization of most industries and a number of technological advancements,

FIGURE 2. Overview of data mining (DM) and some subcategories. Depending on the features included in the data, corresponding tasks can be found: for records that include a temporal dimension tasks such as time-series forecasting and classification are defined, while hot-spot extraction and Geographic Information Systems are found in datasets with spatial characteristics. For records that include both time-related and spatial features, another category of DM tasks is created (Spatio-temporal DM); a subcategory focuses on the study of extracting information from mobility data such as trajectories. Depending on the degree of freedom of the moving object the respective data can be split into two categories: objects that mostly move in a predetermined road network (e.g. trains, taxis and cable-cars) and free space movement (e.g. airplanes, rovers and humans). A subcategory of the latter group relates to maritime mobility, including underwater operations (submarines, autonomous underwater vehicles - AUVs) and surface movement (vessels, autonomous surface vehicles - ASVs, and sailboats).

mainly in communications, has led to large volumes of data being generated and stored daily. These data records may include sensor measurements from Internet-of-Things endpoints [56], biometric patient reports [57], stock trading volumes and prices [58] or air quality sensor data [59]. Constant monitoring has also been utilized in agriculture and smart-farming to study their sustainability [60]. The use of electronic means for enhanced surveillance, such as cameras, has led to the continuous generation of complex data records at a high rate, like video snap-shots of a monitored city block [61]. From the perspective of education, tracing student behavior allows to personalize testing and improve the learning process [62]. Additionally, the great increase in the average amount of time spent online, especially in mobile devices, has resulted in loads of personalized data produced from each individual user, leading to custom marketing based on their indicated taste [63].

Handling big datasets consists of many demanding tasks, each associated with a series of challenges [2], [64], [65]. First, the size of these datasets require advanced solutions for storing and managing the data. Efficient mechanisms are needed even for simple tasks, such as single record retrieval [66], with the study of such tasks being the focus of database management systems (DBMS) and cloud computing. Additionally, the progress in sensor sensitivity and resolution has, in turn, created the need to handle single records of great size, like satellite or medical images [67]. Depending on how these records are intended

to be used, only some of their features can be deemed as essential. Removing irrelevant features reduces the burden of subsequent processing steps and allows for more effective solutions [68]. Moreover, ensuring the quality of each data record is a crucial part of big data processing, as all data-driven applications are inherently dependent on the datasets' accuracy and completeness. Poor data quality can be caused by a plethora of reasons, including but not limited to real-life uncertainty, imprecise measurements, transmission-related errors, or even malicious human intervention [69]. Recognizing noisy records and transforming the input data to produce a reliable and optimal dataset is a major part for any big data application. The mechanisms that have been developed to address such irregularities in the input data may simply rely on filtering out the records based on predetermined expert thresholds, or may use more advanced models to detect inconsistencies through outlier detection [70] or past noise examples [71]. Finally, another technique that has been used to overcome the issues, mainly latency, is to remove data instances that are redundant to the overall scope of the dataset. Besides duplicate removal, this includes the downsampling of the original series of data based on a specific feature, such as the time or area of occurrence [72].

The variety of different categories of data is also an aspect that should be considered when dealing with multiple data sources. The format of the data, in terms of whether they follow a specific schema, plays a crucial part in

how they should be managed and processed [73]. The format may be that of unstructured information, like video streams and signals from sensors, fully structured entries with a strict schema, like bank transactions, as well as data that belong to a middle ground, with both structured and unstructured features (e.g. captioned images). Additionally, combining data of different formats creates the need for specialized fusion techniques that take each data record's context into account [74]. This fusion process can occur in the raw data format or after extracting and transforming the relevant features from each source [75], depending on the heterogeneity of the data.

Beyond collecting and keeping such information, the volume of these datasets creates both the opportunity and the need for further analysis. Interpreting and extracting value from thousands or millions (or even larger in many cases) of records is no simple matter. Simple aggregation methods may provide some basic insights on their nature and distribution, but complex solutions beyond traditional database queries are needed to extract more useful information. The discovery of hidden information and identification of common patterns in datasets has been called exploratory data analysis, or more commonly Data Mining (DM) [4]. The general purpose of all DM methods is to uncover and leverage structural information from a dataset [76], in order to build an accurate representation of it. Depending on the ultimate purpose of each DM task though, different data-driven techniques have been developed.

According to their scope, four major categories can be identified regarding DM-related tasks [77], with the majority of DM problems falling into one or more of these categories: (a) association pattern mining, (b) outlier (anomaly) detection, (c) clustering and (d) classification. The first, association pattern mining, attempts to uncover relations between variables in a dataset. The extracted rules (relationships) may be expressed as if-then statements between features; meaning that the occurrence of a feature in a record would imply the occurrence of one or more other features [78]. The task of outlier or anomaly detection refers to the process of singling out instances in the data that deviate from the rest of the dataset [79]. Although the process is highly dependent on the nature of the input dataset, it can be summed up as extracting a model for “normal” behavior and then isolating records that do not follow this pattern. The anomalies may refer to a single record, simply based on the value of its features, an anomaly with regard to the record's context, meaning its other features, or a group anomaly, where multiple records deviate significantly from the rest [80]. A crucial component of anomaly detection is the definition of the metric used to measure the distance between records (or group of records), since different metrics may point to different anomalies. Several techniques have been proposed to determine anomalies within datasets, based on statistics [81], density measurements or other more advanced methods [82], [83]. As with anomaly detection, the technique

in the next category tries to model normal movement from an unlabeled dataset. More precisely, clustering refers to the partition of a given dataset into groups, so that the records that belong to a specific group are more similar to each other, compared to members of other groups. The number of resulting groups is not known at the beginning but is discovered depending on the input dataset and the “similarity” definition [84]. On the other hand, the classification task refers to the assignment of a label (class) to any given record, from a predetermined set of labels. Given a dataset of annotated records, the goal of classification methods is to extract a model that is capable of modeling the relations between the record attributes and their label, in order to provide accurate annotations on new (unlabeled) samples. Similarly to clustering, the resulting model is highly dependent on the given dataset, but in classification the different data groups are known and given as an input before the start of the processing [85]. The distinction between these two categories can be summed up by the fact that clustering refers to a descriptive method for a given dataset without the resulting groups (or clusters) known beforehand, whilst classification techniques discover relations in annotated data, with regard to a given set of classes, so that they are able to provide a prediction on future entries [86]. Similarly to classification, another major category of DM tasks, the regression models, are extracted from datasets where each record is paired with a target value and can provide an appropriate estimation for this value on new records [87]. In classification, this target value (the class or category) is a label from a discrete set, while in regression, the target value is a continuous numerical variable [88]. Finally, another DM task that has generated a plethora of different works is (automatic) summarization [89], [90]. The purpose of summarization is to generate a brief but comprehensive description of a dataset in an automated way, with the recent advancements of natural language processing (NLP) techniques, especially through neural networks, resulting in a large number of related works in text summarization. Although most of its applications lie with plain text documents, this category may refer to different types of datasets [91], [92], [93].

The growing number of sensors and connected devices, and the frequency of newly produced records from each endpoint, result in a sea of new information to be consumed [94]. Having a resulting DM model that would perform accurately without significant delays is a prerequisite in the modern era of the big-data explosion [95]. Big-data processing can be divided into two categories based on the type of data sources and the urgency for the resulting outcome [96]. Systems that do not have strict limitations with regard to latency are able to use these volumes of data in a more comprehensive manner, called batch processing. This kind of processing is usually aimed at historical datasets and is performed by splitting the data into smaller chunks (or batches). Then repetitive data jobs are performed upon each batch, either sequentially

or in parallel [97]. On the other hand, when dealing with a continuous feed of new data, stream computing is more appropriate. The collection of continuously generated records from multiple sources at a high frequency rate is referred to as data streaming [98]. Another aspect for such solutions is that they more often than not operate in real-time, meaning that they are capable of handling requests and queries within specified time constraints [95]. Subsequently, stream computing is the handling of queries upon data streams, with low latency [99]. This processing distinction can be found in DM as well. For example, suppose we have a set of labeled historical records for the past decade. We are able to model the relationships between the features of this data and their labels through classification. Then an effective classification model could be applied to a stream of newly arrived records, assigning each one with a respective label. The creation of the classification model would be characterized as batch-processing, while utilizing the model to extract new labels is stream-processing. In general, DM in batch processing allows for the extraction of useful insights on the different relationships in large volumes of data through complex mechanisms, while streaming allows for the use of the resulting models in new-coming instances in a timely manner. Furthermore, many DM techniques have been repurposed to handle streaming data exclusively. These algorithms are designed to solve slightly altered problems than their original counterparts, with the result being highly correlated to the order of the data stream. To that sense, clusters in streaming are groups that keep evolving, with a record attributed to different clusters at different points in time [100]. Similarly, classification modeling techniques are altered to continually update the statistics of the decision process [101].

Understanding the nature of a dataset can be achieved through big-data visualization techniques [102]. Data size reduction, like sampling and binned aggregation [103], as well as parallel rendering [104] allow for advanced visualization tools to effectively represent real-world datasets; while the temporal dimension of streaming data can be addressed through dedicated mechanisms [105], [106]. Nevertheless, such techniques alone can rarely fully describe the hidden relationships and patterns unveiled by the aforementioned DM methods [107]. Besides their performance and accuracy, DM models can be evaluated by their ability to depict large datasets in an interpretable way [108]. In recent years, the rise of machine learning (ML) has resulted in new data-driven approaches to study and model datasets [109]. The creation (or training) of a ML model, is an repetitive process that tries to compute an approximation function, by adjusting its initial parameters (or weights) using an indicative given dataset until a desired accuracy threshold is reached [110]. Numerous ML architectures have been proposed, with each one being most suitable for different types of problems [111]. Probably the most prominent family of ML algorithms are based on artificial neural network (NN) architectures, which in turn take inspiration from their

real-life counterparts found in animal brain structures [112], and have proven to be more effective than other traditional DM methods in many cases [113]. The NN approach has been utilized in a large variety of areas [114], from text summarization [115] and real-time object recognition in video streams [116], to speech recognition [117] and disease detection in healthcare-related imagery [118]. However, the degree to which NN models can be interpreted by the users has been a major issue recently [119]. NNs are in general used as “black boxes”, that are fed input sequences and provide a prediction, without revealing the inner workings on how it is computed [120]. This comes as a natural consequence of NNs, and a lot of ML models, as they often constitute an approximation function inextricably linked to the parameters and dataset chosen for training. The lack of transparency in NNs constitutes one of the most significant obstacles in leveraging their accuracy in high-stakes decision systems [108] and adapting them in industry solutions [121]. In other words, simply providing an accurate model is not enough, as details like features prioritization and uncertainty quantification are necessary for human decision to rely on these models [122]. These concerns have been so prominent that a new categorization of ML has spawned recently, namely Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) [123], [124], [125], [126], facilitating transparency and accountability on the models [127].

A. TEMPORAL DATA MINING

As records often refer to events or measurements over time, a separate category of data that includes a temporal dimension is formed, using the following format:

$$p_i = \{t_i, f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{n-1}, f_n\}$$

where, each data record (p_i) is comprised of a time of occurrence (t_i) and a series of other features ($f_i, i \in [0, n]$).

As with generic data, temporal data mining (TDM) is the step of discovering hidden structures and patterns in temporal datasets, as part of the process of Knowledge Discovery in Temporal Databases [128]. Temporal data can be event occurrences or measurements at a specific time point. Additionally, temporal data can refer to summary values over a period of time, like the yearly net income of a company or the number of traffic accidents for a specific month [129]. Since temporal datasets often refer to chronologically arranged observations [130], or time-series, processing such data is called time-series analysis, and the extraction of knowledge from time-series data Time-Series Data Mining (TSDM). Most DM tasks can be directly translated into TDM and TSDM, by adding the temporal dimension into their analysis. Thus new algorithms for temporal classification, temporal clustering, temporal pattern discovery etc. are formed [131].

Depending on how the temporal dimension is handled, different techniques can be utilized for each DM task. For example, clustering for temporal data that have the same time

indication (or timestamp) can be simply performed using classical clustering algorithms. In the case of data streams, where the records arrive ordered according to the time of their occurrence, there are two methods of proceeding [132]. First, a moving time window is applied on the data stream; for each window a clustering is performed upon the data. Then the clusters of neighboring windows are considered for merging, resulting in the final set of clusters. The alternative approach, online clustering, incrementally forms clusters processing the records sequentially, taking into account the degree of shift of the records over time [133], [134], [135], [136]. Moreover, another type of clustering considers time-series as separate objects, using custom metrics for similarity between two full series [137]. These new metrics for distance can be exploited to solve time-series classification problems as well. In this approach the distance between the input series and the ones from the training set is calculated and then a nearest-neighbor based classification then takes place [138]. Alternatively, some multi-step processes exist that involve first transforming the time-series into a feature vector or passing it through a kernel, and then applying a clustering on their processed form exist [139], as well as deep learning (i.e. multi-layered NNs) approaches based on different architecture families [140]. Besides including it as an additional feature, some DM tasks focus on how time influences their outcome. For example, early time-series classification methods attempt to find the optimum point in their consumption of a time-series to determine an accurate enough prediction [141], [142]. For this problem the solutions may rely on tools such as probabilistic classifiers, pattern (shapelet) recognition or mathematical models based on conditional probabilities [143]. This has proven to be extremely effective in time-sensitive domains, such as the study of patient test results in healthcare [144], [145] and production machine maintenance [146], providing timely warnings to the users.

B. SPATIAL DATA MINING

Similarly to time, a dataset may include records with a spatial indication (spatial data) [147], [148], referring to either an event location or the wider area related to the record, as:

$$p_i = \{l_i, f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{n-1}, f_n\}$$

where, each data record (p_i) a collection of features ($f_i, i \in [0, n]$) related to a location (l_i). The spatial dimension may be expressed in different formats and reference systems, including but not limited to 2-D or 3-D location coordinates, street address, city names et al. Spatial data that include geographic coordinate system information are also called geo-spatial data; the software & hardware systems that handle, geo-reference and visualize geo-spatial data are called Geographic Information Systems (GIS) [149].

Traditional DM problems can be more easily conceptualized when dealing with spatial data (spatial data mining - SDM) [5], [150]. For example, clustering can be translated

into finding hotspot areas of events of interest [151], with applications regarding infectious disease outbreaks [152], crime spikes [153] or soil suitability for crop agriculture [154]. The distance metrics utilized in clustering can often be formulas, such as the Pythagorean distance for Cartesian coordinates [155], the haversine distance between geo-referenced points [156] or the Manhattan distance when the space is partitioned into a grid [157].

C. MOBILITY DATA MINING

Naturally, instances that include both temporal and spatial columns constitute a new data category. Spatio-temporal (ST) data can be defined as follows:

$$p_i = \{t_i, l_i, f_0, f_1, \dots, f_{n-1}, f_n\}$$

where, each data record (p_i) a collection of features ($f_i, i \in [0, n]$) occurring at time (t_i) at a location (l_i). As with simple spatial (or temporal) data, the location (or time) can be expressed in a number of ways, depending on the resolution of the measurements, the coordinate system or the usecase in question. For example, instead of coordinates, the city of occurrence may be preferred and instead of a precise timestamp, the day an event happened may be a more suitable choice. Spatio-temporal data analysis and data mining (STDMA) has a vast range of applications, especially in recent years with the rise of big data technologies [158], [159], [160].

Based on the way the temporal and spatial aspects of the records are correlated, ST data can be organized as four separate types [5], [161]:

- 1) **Point reference data** occur when the records focus on the progression of a single monitored variable, usually referring to a wider region rather than focusing on its specific location, with consecutive records not necessarily having the same coordinates. A characteristic example of such data are temperature measurements from weather balloons that move with the wind.
- 2) **Raster data** on the other hand, are measurements from fixed locations in space over time. Such data usually represent the monitoring of an area, with the subset of the data in a specific timestamp providing a snapshot of the current situation. The display selected of the fixed points is directly related to the desired resolution for each snapshot. These data may be medical imaging, such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), or remote sensing, such as satellite images.
- 3) **Event data** are single data instances that include information of an occurrence at a specific time-point and location. These may include a concert event, a crime instance, a traffic accident report, or simply a location transmission from a mobile device.
- 4) Finally, **trajectory data** is a time-stamped series of location points, following the path of the object. These may include a bus itinerary, the movement of a bird, or even the path followed by an unmanned aerial vehicle.

The study of data from the last category (trajectories) and information coming from moving objects, is called mobility data analytics and is one of the most prominent subcategories in STDM [6]. Over the past two decades, the different techniques of monitoring vehicles and human movement has resulted in large amounts of mobility data produced by real-world activity. From automobile urban trips [162], to flight trajectories [163] and even human movement [164], tons of data are generated daily [165], [166]. Applications for mobility DM techniques include, but are not limited to, predicting traffic jams [167], collision avoidance [168], detecting anomalous and illegal movement [169], path planning and optimization [170], and even matters of social and economic interest (like country-relations and market estimations) [171].

In general, a trajectory in a two-dimensional Euclidean space can be denoted as:

$$p_0(x_0, y_0, t_0), p_1(x_1, y_1, t_1), \dots, p_n(x_n, y_n, t_n)$$

where x_i, y_i represents its geographic coordinates time t_i and n is the total number of elements in the series (see example in Figure 3). Apart from positional and temporal features, instances of such data may include additional information, such as the characteristics of the moving objects, their current state of voyage or a summary of the trip in question.

FIGURE 3. A trajectory example. Each point (p_i) depicts the position of the moving object at time t_i , with the option of additional information also included. For instance the course of the object at exact moment of each point is depicted using arrows. In case fewer positions are available, the resulting incomplete trajectory ($p_0 \rightarrow p_7 \rightarrow p_8 \rightarrow p_{16} \rightarrow p_{17}$) may not include instances of interesting activity.

Although the structure for the majority of DM tasks can be translated into mobility data as well, traditional techniques for these problems have not been that effective and do not translate well. Due to the unique nature of ST data, the need for a new set of algorithms has appeared [5]. First, ST are by definition self-correlated, meaning that different instances are not independent from one another. In other DM applications, the records are defined mostly as independent to each other, with any possible relation being the focus of dedicated pattern

extraction tasks. For example, the bank transactions from the same account may not be at all related and depict a normal set of purchases. Uncovering an explicit relationship between these transactions requires an advanced method to identify possible complex events like fraud [172]. On the other hand, the position of a moving object at a certain time is highly dependent on both its past positions but also on other instances of nearby objects at that period.

Another challenge found in ST data, is that they, along with their underlying patterns [159], highly rely on environmental parameters. The movement in highways and suburban areas is completely different in terms of speed, traffic and maneuverability. Although some data-series may appear to have high spatial similarity, the type of movement is completely related to extrinsic parameters, like the nature of the moving object, the overall traffic during the voyage or the specific location of the moving object's destination. For example, a bicycle may follow the same path at night that a taxi would do in the morning, but the daily traffic would have affected the second's behavior much more indicating different types of ST activity. Moreover, the distribution of ST data is not constant with respect to time. From a statistical point of view, this phenomenon, also called temporal nonstationarity [160], can be expressed as a significant shift with time in the mean and variance values. As an example, due to the seasonality of tourism, human-generated mobility data increases dramatically in the summer months in a lot of seaside destinations, compared to the end of the year [173]. The same applies to trajectories in various weather conditions, like in bird migration [174]. These characteristics constitute a major obstacle in knowledge transferability [26], as models are completely tied to the characteristics of the dataset used during the extraction process. Thus, a pattern found in human urban mobility should not be assumed to appear in zebra herds. Likewise, an algorithm that allows for traffic predictions in the US can not be expected to work as well in the Middle East. Hence, the algorithms created for handling mobility data should be able to address this issue.

The recent advances in autonomous vehicle technology has created new challenges for mobility data analytics. Autonomous transportation refers to vehicles that are able to move and operate partly or completely without human intervention, and in many cases without the presence of human personnel. The design of such vehicles, is made possible through small and reliable control systems, accurate sensors capable of operating in challenging conditions and long-range transceivers. Such implementations can be found in all types of transportation from self-driving rovers [175], cars [176] and trucks [177], to unmanned aerial (drones) and underwater vehicles [178], [179] and have been so advanced that they are even utilized in military operations [180], [181], [182]. Moreover, the emergence of some solutions created from off-the-shelf open products in the past few years, indicate an upcoming rise in their popularity for the near future [183], [184], [185]. As these vehicles are

designed to operate in unknown dynamic environments, along other moving objects, a critical aspect of their design is ensuring safety while traveling [186]. For this purpose, they rely on visual and inertial sensors to determine possible collisions and the state of other nearby objects [187], leading to situational awareness through fast algorithmic implementations [188]. Determining safe pathways and accurately predicting near-future movements is crucial in order to ensure accident avoidance. The first can be executed offline, by extracting common pathways of safe movement for the vehicles through big mobility DM on historical data. For more solid results, the characteristics of the autonomous vehicle and the goal of its trip should be incorporated on these models. For the second, accurate and fast algorithms are required to determine the movement of neighboring objects in the near future through pattern matching and forecasting techniques. Finally, since the sensor detections may be in a different format (such as video streams, radar detections, etc.), the respective methods should be able to handle fusing heterogeneous data in an effective manner [189].

Following the structure of DM, works related to trajectory data are categorized into larger types [19]. First, classifying the trajectories in a set of predetermined groups, can be semantically translated as determining the type of movement; which can be further interpreted as labeling the transportation mode of a specific segment of the trajectory or recognizing the purpose of the trip [21]. Preparing the trajectories to have an appropriate format is a critical part of the classification process [190]. This may include spatio-temporal interpolation or downsampling, so that all trajectories have the same amount of location points or for temporal alignment of their sampling. Additionally, trajectory segmentation is employed to split the movement into meaningful parts, based on either their duration, or some other semantically noteworthy events (like a turn or a stop). As with all classification techniques, the selection of features that will be used for the classification is of utmost importance. These may include simple ST features like speed, distance traveled between data records and rate of turn, but also include features that are specific to the use case, like heart rate, remaining fuel, social environment attributes of the area et al. Afterwards, traditional classification techniques, such as Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees or Dynamic Bayesian Networks, can be applied to the resulting sub-trajectories [21]. A simple example for trajectory classification can be found in mobility data originating from a mobile phone. The aforementioned methods can be used to determine the intervals where the person was walking, taking the bus, using the subway or riding a bicycle during their day [191].

Trajectory clustering, as its traditional counterpart, attempts to uncover groups with similar mobility characteristics. Depending on what the ultimate purpose of this process is, different techniques have been proposed [20]. Grouping trajectories without taking time into account,

uncovers common routes followed in a trajectory dataset. Contrarily, considering the temporal dimension results in finding trajectory instances where the objects moved in a close proximity to one another. Another approach, following similar steps to trajectory classification, tries to compute the distance between path segments, instead of the full trips. Such patterns of movement often occur in animal-mobility related problems, like identifying flocks of birds in motion or swarm behavior. Lastly, the uncovering of hotspot areas of interest, like slow movement areas or stationary regions, can be achieved through this process.

A challenging aspect of clustering, as well as trajectory classification [192], is the selection of an appropriate similarity metric. When dealing with single geo-spatial data (points), the haversine distance has proven to be the most widely-used metric. Since trajectories consist of multiple points, the distance between two locations should be adapted into a larger schema that takes their temporal dimension into account. Depending on the format of the (sub-)trajectories and the scope of the problem, a different metric can be used to compare two trajectories. For example, for trajectories that are equally interpolated (with the same number of points at the same timestamps), simply averaging the Euclidean/haversine distance may be sufficient enough; this approach is called Mean Absolute Error (MAE). More complex metrics can be employed otherwise [193]. Four similarity measures have been identified as the most important and impactful in ST data processing [194]. More precisely, Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) first matches all trajectory points so that consecutive points from the same trajectory are either matched to the same point or consecutive ones from the second [195]. This approach allows for overcoming differences in movement speeds, since besides the ordering of the data points it ignores the temporal feature. In similar fashion, the Discrete Fréchet distance (DFD), and its continuous variant, matches the curvature of two trajectories, focusing on the maximum distance between the matched points instead of the total/average [196]. On the contrary, the Longest Common Subsequence (LCSS) method allows for points to be left unmatched, by skipping them, as it attempts to find the length of the larger points sequence present in two trajectories [197]. As real coordinates rarely have the same exact values, approaches like the LCSS are better utilized in transformed location sequences like road segments. Moreover, objects may move in an extremely similar manner but in completely different areas. For instance, the unique “skipping” maneuver of Hypersonic Glide Vehicles (HGVs), may be performed regardless of the part of the world the HGV is flying over [198]. In this case, the trajectory segments should be transformed (e.g. scaled) or moved to a common area, to be able to measure their similarity. For such formats, the Edit Distance on Real sequence (EDR), another option originating from string comparison and number sequences, measures the number of edits (replaces, insertions or deletes) of members of the

trajectories, and is best fit for such normalized (scaled) ST data [199].

The relatively high computational complexity of the aforementioned, traditional similarity-measurement methods may often result in significant delays during processing. In order to facilitate faster distance calculations between trajectories, several deep learning techniques have been proposed recently [200]. The main idea behind these methods is the transformation of the input trajectories into a more compact format; largely through representation learning. Inspired by the effectiveness of translating words into vectors [201], representation learning has been used upon different input data types, such as graphs [202] and video streams [203]. In the case of trajectories, a prominent example of this process can be found in the work of Li et al. [204], introducing their *t2vec* technique. With the new trajectory representation the computation of traditional similarity measurements (like the LCSS and the Edit distance) can be completed in linear-time [200], [204], [205]. A low-dimensional feature vector is also computed in the work of Liang et al. [206], with image representations of the input trajectories. These representations are then fed into an encoder-decoder architecture to capture the trajectory-level features by optimizing a reconstruction process of the unlabeled training data. In order to also incorporate point-level features into the resulting model, the work in [207] proposes a different approach. First, to overcome the lack of trajectory data pairs for the training process, self-supervising techniques are used. This entails that the input trajectories are slightly distorted in order to create new positive sample trajectories, that are similar to the ground truth, thus augmenting the training set. For the purpose of accuracy, contrastive learning is also employed, by including significantly dissimilar (negative) samples for each trajectory during training. This way, the model is better fitted to the positive samples that were created from the true trajectories. The combination of contrastive learning and two types of distortion types (trajectory and point level) for the self-supervised data augmentation achieves significant improvement in performance compared to other approaches. Contrastive learning is again utilized in [208], where the area of interest is modeled using regional graphs and then each input trajectory is passed through a graph neural network; in the end using the Euclidean distance between the resulting vectors for the similarity.

In addition to the pattern extraction, clustering and classification, a major category of trajectory data processing entails predicting the future behavior of the moving object. This category comes natural for mobility data, as trajectories are essentially time-series but also due to the self-correlation of its nature, as future positions of a moving object directly affect other objects. The main task in this category is predicting the future locations of an object. That may include the future coordinates at a specific time point or a more complete description of its path. Path prediction can in turn be split into short-term and long-term forecasts depending on the temporal horizon of the predicted path, but this distinction

is not clear and is subject to interpretation according to the mobility type (human movement, taxi rides, airplane flights, etc.) or use case. Most approaches rely on mobility patterns found in historical information to provide an accurate prediction. The respective methods are also characterized by the information required by their prediction algorithm. More precisely, besides the current position of a moving object, some algorithms may need to look further back at past positions to provide a forecast. Some approaches utilize other types of information, like the reported trip destination, to determine the best suited prediction. A similar task is trip recommendation for a moving object, where according to the requirements of the user, the best alternative route is given using optimization techniques. The parameters taken into account may include the total duration of the trip [209], fuel consumption [210] or weather forecasts [211].

Creating models that can estimate future events and attributes, besides just the predicted path, have been the focus of numerous studies. First, a task related to predicted movement is the estimation of future traffic in a specific area [212]. More precisely, traffic can be expressed as the total number of moving objects present or the number of vehicles entering or leaving the area (traffic flow). These definitions can be addressed either as a numerical time-series problem or through aggregating on the predicted paths of all objects near the area. Additionally, traffic may be represented as a predicted mean speed over an area or a hotspot identifications, singling out areas of high predicted congestion [213]. Another important problem in predictive analytics is the accurate estimation of the arrival time at the destination (Estimated Time of Arrival - ETA) [214]. This estimation can be achieved by calculating the duration of a forecasted path (possibly considering the predicted traffic as mentioned above), through averages from historical data, or by transforming the problem into a regression for real numbers and using traditional prediction techniques (such as Random Forests and Support Vector machines). The returned ETA predicted refers to a given destination point (e.g., bus stops, train stations, airports). In case the trip destination is not reported beforehand, there are dedicated works that attempt to predict it [215], [216]. Finally, more complex events, such as the possible collision between two moving objects, can be extracted either using the forecasted future trajectories or through risk assessment techniques [217].

III. VESSEL TRAJECTORY DATA

In this work we focus on maritime mobility, and more specifically on processing trajectory data from marine vessels (Figure 4). In this section, we describe the unique nature of maritime mobility data, the users of interest and provide an overview on the available data sources.

A. THE MARITIME USE CASE

Vessel mobility includes freight transport, fishing, passenger transportation, military or law enforcement missions, and

even pleasure voyages (e.g. yachts and cruise ships). As a result, processing trajectory data can be useful for a variety of end users. For example, passengers and travel agencies rely on vessel mobility analysis for trip planning, while port authorities and taxi drivers may use predictive analytics to better organize their operations. Here we provide a brief description for some major stakeholders across the shipping industry:

- **Vessel operators:** While the vessel is underway, its captain and crew are responsible for its safe and efficient operation; that is moving between selected ports and anchorages safely, on time and considering the international laws of transportation at sea. Analysis of maritime trajectories can be useful in two distinct ways for their part. First, while vessels usually follow predetermined routes toward their destination, past tracks can unveil safe passages and trends of movement, for the captain and officers to take into account, while planning their trip before departure. The estimated time of arrival at the destination port and vessel-specific characteristics, such as its size, age or type of cargo it carries, are also major factors for such planning. Historical trajectory analysis, can provide useful insights regarding selected paths [218], [219], [220]. For example the average vessel speed over different areas can be utilized to provide an estimation for the arrival of the vessel and the weather conditions it may face if selecting a certain path. Moreover, route extraction techniques can highlight areas of low traffic, indicating undocumented dangers for crossing vessels. Besides planning, trajectory analytics are also useful during trips, where ship operators can incorporate the vessel's current positioning and state for maritime situational awareness. Analysis on the state of its environment, such as the tracks of nearby vessels, can produce timely warnings for possible collisions and suggest safe paths to follow [38], [44]. Newfound information can also be fed into dynamic models, to provide alternative routes in the case of extreme events or high traffic congestion. An indicative example for such use case, can be found in the Suez canal obstruction incident of 2021, where a 400m-long container vessel blocked the passage for a period of 6 days. During this situation, vessels that planned to cross the canal opted for alternative routes, mostly going around the continent of Africa. Advanced dynamic analytics on the vessel trajectories would have been useful to determine the shift in traffic across the globe and the effects of selecting one of the alternative paths for each vessel [221]. For smaller vessels, having a clear picture of the high traffic areas can help with creating safer paths during voyaging, e.g. fishing or recreational sailing.
- **Fleet management:** With a portion of over 80% of the total volume of international trade in goods carried by sea the last few years [222], [223], efficient spatial

planning of commercial shipping operations is a task of high importance. Extracting accurate insights, like the port arrival time, can lead to more efficient planning regarding cargo distribution into different vessel trips, thus optimizing the delays during shipping. Predicting port congestion, where vessels are not able to berth due to high traffic, can also aid in such operations. The scarcity of available berths may indicate slower movement to be a better alternative in order to reach the destination at a more appropriate time, as high speeds lead to higher fuel consumption [224]. Another factor troubling shipowners and fleet managers is cargo loss, due to mechanical failures, groundings or extreme weather-related phenomena [225], [226]. Analysis on past trajectories and incidents, along with predictive analytics, can contribute in creating risk assessment mechanisms to prevent such accidents.

- **Coastguard and port authorities:** Local and international authorities monitor vessel movement to detect possible illegal operations or help in instances where human life at sea is in danger. In order to track vessels in an effective and reliable way, multiple data sources can be fused, using advanced mobility data techniques [227]. With the goal of ensuring safe voyaging at sea, authorities may use mobility data to provide warnings to ships of possible accidents and prevent incidents with catastrophic consequences, like oil spills in the ocean [228]. Detecting illegal activities, such as fishing instances in protected areas, piracy incidents or unreported ship-to-ship cargo transfers are also of interest. Multiple works can be found in the literature that propose a data driven analysis for such phenomena [229], [230], [231].

Since a large portion of the world's trade is carried by vessels, analyzing their traffic patterns can be extremely helpful in recognizing shipping trends. Focusing on cargo and tanker ships, relationships between commercial ports can be uncovered without the need of detailed information regarding the commodities themselves [232]. Dedicated studies on historical trajectories related to energy sources, such as oil or natural gas, can assist in determining the respective trade network [233], [234] and the impact of the market price fluctuations upon it [235]. Mobility data can also be exploited in order to extract freight rate predictions based on vessel movement [236], [237]. On top of that, both the economic and the environmental impact of implementing stricter emission-related policies can also be evaluated by maritime mobility analytics [238], [239].

Monitoring vessel movement on a large scale also allows for observing the economic consequences of complex international events [240], [241]. For instance, the impact of the COVID-19 outbreak on global trade can be assessed by comparing vessel traffic before and during the period of the pandemic [242]. This can be achieved by analyzing the vessel behavior with regards to port and anchoring areas [243] and

by studying the shift in the traffic flow upon well-established trade routes [244]. Similarly, the effect of conflicts and wars on exports and trade is also apparent through spatio-temporal data analysis. As an example, the Russia–Ukraine conflict has altered the global shipping network by significantly decreasing maritime activities in the Black and Adriatic seas [245], while simultaneously tightening alliances of other countries [246].

FIGURE 4. An example of processing vessel trajectory data. In (a) positional messages from several vessels are depicted in different colours. Extracted patterns of movement can help identify outlier points (b), resulting in more accurate filtered data (c). Recognition and segmentation algorithms can identify interesting activities, like trawling (d), while predictive analytics can provide a forecast on the future movement of the vessel (e) or an estimated time of arrival (ETA) at its destination port (f).

From a data processing perspective, vessel movement provides unique opportunities for analysis mainly due to the ships' different transportation modes and the availability of data:

- The large variety of ship types allows for different scenarios to be studied. Larger vessels that carry heavy loads only travel between ports and anchorages, mainly for safety reasons, and move with limited maneuverability. Contrarily, smaller boats often follow more complex patterns and may make round trips to the origin point of departure. Such activities may include commercial or recreational fishing, sailing or yacht voyages. Moreover, other ship types (pilot and tug boats) are designed to operate alongside other vessels, either to guide them in challenging waters due to their lack of mobility. Other types of ships, namely search-and-rescue (SAR) boats and coast guard patrol vessels, operate solely to ensure safety at sea and are often associated with critical events. The activities of military vessels can be treated as a separate category. Since vessel mobility can be linked to commercial shipping,

energy, transportation, and even sport, the applications of relative analytics are equally vast.

- Apart from their “type”, other physical characteristics of the vessels can also affect their movement patterns. Smaller vessels typically travel close to the coast and avoid areas with severe weather, while larger vessels can navigate in open waters and generally prefer to operate far from land. Besides their dimensions, their design also plays a crucial part, as vessels like tankers, with their hulls mostly underwater, are significantly affected by the underwater currents. Wind is more important for container vessels, where a larger portion of the ship is above the waterline.
- For ensuring safety at sea, the vessels are constantly monitored by the port authorities, fleet managers and other stakeholders, through a variety of techniques. Today, over 200 thousand ships from around the globe operate daily, leading to the generation of large volumes of new data on a daily basis. With vessel tracking systems and systems operating for more than 15 years, big DM methods can exploit these large historical datasets to accurately model vessel behaviour [45], [47]. We expand on the different data sources for vessel movement in the following section.

B. DATA SOURCES FOR MARITIME MOBILITY

Overall, different techniques can be found in the literature for tracking vessel movement. Depending on the participation of the vessels themselves in that process, we can distinguish two types of vessel monitoring (Figure 5).

Remote Sensing includes all means to observe a ship's movement without its active participation or consent. The capabilities of advanced sensors are exploited in order to provide an accurate depiction of the current state. For their translation of the sensors' images and measurements into positional records, dedicated custom mechanisms can be found in the literature, depending on the type of information. The global reach of satellite imagery allows for a monitoring vessel traffic with high-resolution images produced daily [53]. For example, the European Space Agency (ESA) earth observation programme Copernicus¹ provides images free to the public, from two satellite missions (Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2). The first, uses synthetic-aperture radars to capture earth at all times (night and day), while the other produces optical images of high spatial resolution (up to 10m). Vessel positions can be extracted from those images through deep learning image processing [247], [248], [249]. A different process is followed for each data source, as for optical imagery weather-related factors, like clouds, can obstruct the satellite's view. Port surveillance solutions utilize similar, usually static, means to detect vessel movement within the the port confines. For example, well-placed cameras can be used to determine the appearance of a vessel [250], [251] and, combined with other sources, allow

¹<https://www.copernicus.eu/en>

for more accurate situational awareness [252], [253]. Other approaches for real-time monitoring of areas of interest, rely on the autonomous drone technology for coastal and marine regions [253], [254], [255], [256]. Moreover, on-board sensors are the most reliable source for situational awareness for underway vessels or submersed watercrafts, like submarines. Systems like Sonar (Sound Navigation and Ranging) has been used for several decades, to provide accurate depictions of nearby traffic [257]. The recent rise of autonomous and unmanned vehicles with regards to maritime transportation, has also created a domain for solutions that largely rely on remote sensor techniques. With no crew members on board, the vehicles rely on advanced sensors, like cameras and radar, to detect approaching vessels [189]. Another sensor category that can be found in this solutions is LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging), suitable for high resolution laser scanning [185], [189], [258].

Self-reporting systems rely on the vessel's technology and crew to report on their movement. More precisely, on-board transmitters send the vessel's position and attributes so that nearby receivers, including other vessels, are able to track its movement. Several relevant systems have been proposed over the years [15], [259], with some being mandatory by the International Maritime Organization (IMO) under its Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) conventions. A major example is the Long-range identification and tracking (LRIT) system, established in 2006 by IMO, that forces ships to transmit their position and identity information (such as their flag) when requested by an authorized agency [260], [261]. LRIT messages have a range of 1000 nautical miles off-shore and can be decrypted only by the respective data centres, responsible for receiving and storing such information, with access given solely to contracting governmental organisations [15]. In a more focused effort, the Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) includes messages with positional and mobility features, for real-time monitoring the activities of commercial fishing vessels [262], [263]. Through the use of VMS, authorities are able to track current fishing activities of relatively large vessels, and detect possible operations in unauthorized areas. The most widely used system used around the world is the IMO-reinforced Automatic Identification System (AIS), mandated in 2004. Originally intended for collision avoidance, AIS is currently leveraged in various aspects of maritime operations; platforms such as <https://www.marinetraffic.com/> provide invaluable insights for the shipping industry. Besides positional reports, information regarding the vessel's dimensions, state or destination can also be found in the AIS messages. Depending on the current speed of the vessel, consecutive messages may be from a couple of seconds to a few minutes apart [248].

IV. DATA PREPARATION

After acquiring a dataset comprised of vessel trajectories, several techniques should be employed to both ensure the quality of each record and prepare it for further analysis. This entails recognizing and removing incomplete and erroneous

data points and transforming them according to the needs of the analysis task, through compression or segmentation. On top of these steps, a process that deals with extremely sparse trajectories can generate repaired path samples, to enhance the dataset, instead of discarding them altogether.

A. PREPROCESSING

In order to create a reliable and optimized trajectory dataset, few preprocessing steps are necessary. Such mechanisms can be found in most works and are designed to keep data-points and trajectories of high quality, in terms of their accuracy, completeness and formatting. Identifying and removing faulty or unnecessary positional records is the initial step of this process [264]. Positional inaccuracies in the messages may be the result of systematic and technical errors during the generation and transmission of the data [265]. Messages whose spatial characteristics are by definition incorrect (do not represent valid positions), can be automatically discarded. The same applies to positions that do not lie in sea and river areas, but are on land. For this "land-masking" [266], detailed representations of sea-areas should be used, keeping as a result only the messages that lie within. Furthermore, identifying instances of improbable transitions between consecutive messages is another approach for removing incorrect records. For example, messages that indicate an extreme speed for the vessels should be considered as possible irregularities. During this process, it is common that the speed feature is re-calculated based on the spatial and temporal characteristics of consecutive messages, instead of using the reported values [248]. Kalman filtering [267] can also be used for removing and modifying outlier points, by comparing them with predictions for future positions [268], [269].

Depending on the source of information, vessel trajectories may be of extreme length. This can be attributed to either the large duration of their trips (e.g. transatlantic voyages of cargo vessels) or the high sampling rate [49], especially in AIS datasets. Vessel trajectory compression is the task of reducing the size of ship trajectory by removing data points, losing as little useful information as possible. This can be executed on full trajectories after their completion, or through online processing of each new positional message [40]. The respective algorithms are defined by which features of the moving vessel they take into account. A common approach, the Douglas-Peucker algorithm, takes advantage of the spatial characteristics of the vessel's path, measuring the possible distance between candidate points and keeping the ones that fall under a threshold [270], [271]. The difference in mobility-related features of (such as speed, heading or distance traveled) of consecutive trajectory points are often used as an indication [272]. A sliding window is often utilized to effectively handle a few data at a time [273]. In order to overcome the high sensitivity to input thresholds and parameters, the proposed solution of Fikioris et al. takes advantage of genetic algorithms and incremental optimization for tuning, according to each vessel type [274].

FIGURE 5. Two distinct categories of vessel tracking data sources can be found, depending on the role of the moving object. In case the object is tracked without its consent or knowledge, remote sensing techniques, like SONAR, LiDAR or Optical imagery, are exploited. On the other hand, self-reporting systems, such as the AIS or LRIT, rely on the vessel's themselves to report on their position in a frequent or periodic manner.

Transforming the trajectories from a series of positional points into a series of segments allows for more accurate classification, clustering and pattern recognition. The process of splitting an input trajectory into different sub-trajectories is called segmentation. Compression and segmentation are closely related problems, trying to provide a summary of a trajectory [275]. A simple way to segment the trajectories can be based on the speed of the vessel (differentiating between underway or moored stages [276]) or predetermined areas like ports and known fishing spots. Selecting the appropriate “change” point can be a complex task, as it usually requires determining universally applicable thresholds [277]. The effect of different segmentation algorithms on vessel type classification was studied in [278]. Moreover, creating a series of road segments (map-matching) from the input trajectories, is a common approach in urban mobility DM [279], [280]. The resulting road sequences can more easily be utilised in tracking moving objects and navigation recommendation, as well as mapping an area by locating new segments [281]. Since a road network is not available for maritime mobility, this process is a complex task, addressed mainly by clustering techniques, as discussed in the next chapters.

B. TRAJECTORY RECONSTRUCTION

The sampling rate of vessel trajectory data varies, depending on the source. For remote sensing, area coverage and temporal sampling are correlated to the specifications of the sensors, like the range of a LiDAR sensor or the characteristics of a satellite's orbit. For the self-reporting systems, two factors affect the sampling rate. First, the frequency of transmission by the vessel itself set the limitations for the extracted dataset. This is addressed by the AIS, as messages of moving

vessels may occur every few seconds [282], minimizing the distance between the real trajectory and its transmitted data representation. On the other hand, the receiving end is also responsible for the quality of that data. Coverage issues are often an obstacle in a terrestrial network of AIS receivers, since open waters are often out of their range. AIS dataset collected from satellites are used to deal with this difficulty, reaching areas far from the coast. In this case though, the quality of the collected data is affected by both limitations similar to the ones in remote sensing, and the issue of packet collision [283], that may result in discarding a lot of messages from smaller or non-commercial vessels.

In general, there exist instances where the vessel trajectory data are unacceptably sparse, having large spatial or temporal gaps between their positions. Since these incomplete trajectories cannot be considered as accurate representations of the vessels' movement, they should not be included in the process of knowledge extraction. For instance, in Figure 3 the movement indicated by orange lines ($p_0 \rightarrow p_7 \rightarrow p_8 \rightarrow p_{16} \rightarrow p_{17}$) does not encapsulate the activity of the moving object, while the blue trajectory is closer to the truth.

Instead of discarding them completely, several trajectory reconstruction strategies have been proposed. Several works assume that at least in theory, the trajectory of a ship can be approximated as a straight line for a short time period. Therefore, linear interpolation is a widely used gap-filling method [284], [285], [286], [287], where kinematic equations take mobility characteristics of the vessel (i.e. speed, acceleration, course and rate-of-turn) to provide an estimation of the intermediate positions [288]. However, this method is only suitable for small forecasting windows (e.g., several minutes), high frequency data and in situations when the vessel is expected to follow a uniform linear motion. Additional interpolation methods have been proposed, such

as polynomial, cubic spline, Lagrange and Hermite interpolation methods, which take into consideration additional features such as direction, heading and speed to reconstruct trajectories with curves [286], [289]. Based on Fermat's spiral fitting, [290] provides an estimation for the vessel's curve of movement, after several steps of preprocessing and denoising. Unfortunately, the above methods do not take into account the environment or prior information regarding a travel area. They also show degraded accuracy in scenarios where ships conduct maneuvers often (e.g., rivers). [291] leverages near-by trajectories to the one with the missing segment to extract a synthetic estimation of the vessel's route. Two other approaches first assign a navigational state on each vessel position before moving on to the reconstruction. More precisely, [276] determines whether the vessel is at a hoteling state (berthing), maneuvering with the help of tug vessels (in which case a linear regression model smooths the trajectory) or traveling on a normal speed (where a parametric spline is used). Similarly, [292] distinguishes the vessel movement into mooring and voyaging. Focusing on the second state, linear interpolation is used for trajectory segments that appear to be moving on a straight line, while cubic spline [293] is used for the rest. DM approaches rely on unsupervised methods [294] or neural networks [295], [296], [297] to provide a possible path, based on knowledge extracted from historical trajectories of the area. For example, the authors of [298] transform the input trajectory into a 2D gridded representation and pass it through a complex deep learning structure (namely through U-Net Convolutional Networks) to reconstruct trajectories, especially in cases with high rates of turn and loss rate. As this problem can be translated into route forecasting (where the destination point is known), several of the methods described in the relevant following section can also be employed.

V. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYTICS

Several works found in the literature focus on capturing vessel traffic in a descriptive manner. The proposed methods are able to model normal vessel behavior and provide insights on given input trajectories. The most prominent DM tasks found in this category are the extraction of routes of common movement and the detection of anomalous behavior of vessels (Table 1) or their participation in specific activities of interest (Table 2).

A. ANOMALY DETECTION

The main reason behind the maritime surveillance and monitoring systems is the assurance of safety at seas and accurate risk assessment. Abnormal and dangerous behavior can be related to the vessel's position, its direction and speed of movement or its relative motion to other ships [28]. Detecting simple events like illegal passage over a restricted area or high velocities does not require DM. More complex behaviors though can be detected by first modeling normal movement in an area and then by labeling remarkable

deviations as anomalies [29]. For this purpose, methods like the Gaussian Mixture Models or Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) model the multivariate inputs (trajectory points) by extracting a distribution and a probability density function respectively [299]. A new input that does not conform to this modeling, i.e. has a lower likelihood than the training data, is labeled as an anomaly. Another approach is based on mobility route extraction, as instances where vessels either follow paths outside the extracted common routes or move in the opposite direction are flagged [300]. The timeliness in detecting irregular behavior is of high importance, for ensuring safety at sea. Chatzikokolakis et al. address this issue, by proposing a distributed service with sub-second latency in real conditions [301]. Their system is able to detect dangerous or suspicious behavior such as route deviation, sailing in shallow waters and communication gaps accurately.

Two types of anomalies can be found explicitly in self-reporting systems data [30]. First, the intentional disruption of the transmission of positional AIS messages occurs so that the presence of a vessel is hidden to nearby observers. The purpose for this AIS switch-off event can either be to hide improper activities, to keep areas of interest secret (e.g. fishing spots) or to avoid detection by pirate vessels [230]. An approach for such anomalies is based on the signal processing parameters by using the AIS message strength to extract a threshold for each base receiver and estimate the lack of transmissions accordingly [302]. Moreover, vessel signals in open waters are often sparse due to lack of good-enough coverage. Bernabé et al. address this issue by determining the possibility of receiving a message in an area using deep learning and flagging inconsistencies with the real data [303]. The other type of anomaly, known as spoofing, refers to the use of another vessel's identification or the transmission of false trajectories, to hide the real paths followed [304], [305]. Cryptographic authentication on the transmission device for the trajectory messages can be exploited for accurate spoofing detection as indicated in [306]. d'Afflisio et al. presented a series of works focused on this problem, based on multiple hypothesis testing, using statistical models to estimate the likelihood of such behavior [307], [308].

B. ROUTE EXTRACTION

Vessel mobility patterns can be modeled using various representations. Extracting common routes provides a street-like view of maritime traffic that is easily interpreted and can be useful for different types of applications, like anomaly detection and path forecasting [28], [43]. A lot of works use the extracted geometries to generate a traffic network as their next step. Most works found in the literature are based on clustering techniques, since the number or format of resulting routes are not known beforehand. For example, [310] considers both direction and speed variations to group nearby vessel points and thus detect main traffic routes, while [311] uses an agglomerative algorithm to create a hierarchical tree of the clusters. Following a different approach Murray and

TABLE 1. Some of the most prominent works regarding anomaly detection and route extraction from vessel trajectory data, with the major methods utilized and the

Task	Work	Method(s) Utilized	Year
Anomaly Detection	[299]	Gaussian Mixture Model / Kernel Density Estimator	2015
	[302]	Support Vector Machine / Averaged RSSI Raster	2017
	[301]	Lambda architecture	2019
	[300]	DBSCAN	2020
	[304]	Fusion (AIS & Radar)	2020
	[230]	Coverage grid	2020
	[307], [308]	Generalized likelihood ratio testing / Model-order selection	2021
	[306]	Public key cryptography	2022
	[303]	Transformer	2023
Route Extraction	[309]	Genetic algorithm	2016
	[310]	DBSCAN	2016
	[311]	Agglomerative clustering	2017
	[312]	Douglas-Peucker	2017
	[313]	Delaunay Triangulation	2019
	[314]	Adaptive K-means	2020
	[315]	Lagrange & DBSCAN	2021
	[316]	Representation learning & HDBSCAN	2021
	[317]	DBSCAN & Kernel Density Estimation	2022
	[318]	H3 grid indexing	2024

Perera in [316], rely on representation learning to transform the input trajectories into vectors of fixed size and then apply standard clustering techniques. A large group of methods, rely on the identification of points of high importance within the input trajectories (i.e. waypoints), ensuring that critical decisions, such as significant turns, or other activities to be considered [317]. Such a method is proposed in [309], where a genetic algorithm extracts route waypoints, in order to address the varying traffic density of the data. and turns them into a mobility graph. Similarly, [312] identifies points with significant direction change on historical AIS trajectories using the Douglas-Peucker simplification algorithm and then incorporates a merging mechanism to generate a maritime traffic network. A multi-step pipeline is also proposed in the work by Kontopoulos et al. [315]. Vessel trajectories are split into sub-sequences, based on points where vessels tend to spend a significant amount of time stationary. Then, vessel movement between waypoints is modeled through a novel clustering technique based on DBSCAN that takes the speed and the course attributes of the moving vessels into account. The inclusion of the Lagrange method for interpolating the trajectories allows for the approach to handle even sparse AIS data. The end results include a representation of common vessel traffic in an area of interest, regardless of the vessels' destinations or characteristics. Even though, the extraction process usually focuses on vessel traffic regardless of the trips' purpose, splitting the AIS data based on selected criteria can provide a more accurate and descriptive depiction of mobility patterns. The ROTA algorithm presented in [314], is applied for subsets of a global AIS dataset, before applying an adaptive K-means clustering. Each subset corresponds to a specific pair of origin and destination ports, and a specific vessel type. The extracted geometries (convex-hulls)

are filtered based on both the number of positions included and the number of the respective trips, together with their total area., to cover the majority of traffic in each case (73-78%). Instead of trying to extract the geometry shapes from scratch, few approaches split the mobility space into cells and map vessel activity accordingly. For example, [313] passes the raw AIS data into a grid structure to determine traffic density for each cell, and through adaptive thresholding and adapting filtering they are merged into shipping lanes. Each new trajectory is then easily mapped into a series of segments, from a road network created between the smoothed lanes. In [318] the grid-based network is enhanced with historical mobility statistics, based on hexagonal cells,² thus incorporating common mobility patterns, but also route specific features, like the vessels top destinations.

C. ACTIVITY RECOGNITION

In the context of vessel mobility data, several activities of interest can be identified. Besides operations occurring inside port areas and normal voyaging, vessels may take part in other well-defined activities. For example, the interaction between two vessels (or more) has produced several analyses and studies over the years. More precisely, the risk of a possible collision between the vessels has been the focus of several works regarding safe navigation, especially with the emergence of autonomous vehicle technology [319], [320]. Two tasks can be identified regarding such occurrences, with some work providing solutions for both. A risk assessment analysis extracts alerts regarding possible near-future collisions [321], [322], while dedicated systems provide feasible avoidance manoeuvres for the ships to follow [319], sometimes incorporating the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREGs) [13]. Unusually close proximity of moving vessels may also indicate interesting activity to be explored. For instance, large ships require the assistance of smaller boats, like pilot of tugboats, during berthing operations or for crossing shallow waters [323]. Another use case involves a possible rendezvous event between the vessels, indicating suspicious activity, like illegal transshipment [324]. Analyses on possible meeting points were conducted for the cases of positional messages interruption in [325] or for future events in [326]. Moreover, a rule-based system has explored all three mentioned use cases in [327] and [328].

Here we focus on the movement of a single vessel; we discuss the major activity types and the present indicative approaches found in the literature, summarized in Table 2.

The case where vessels spend an unusual amount of time in a specific area without significant movement is called loitering and may indicate suspicious behavior. In [327], loitering is modeled by a rule, finding stopped or slow-moving vessels away from the coast, that are not anchored, for over 30 minutes. Several approaches

²The generation of the cells used Uber's H3 structure: <https://www.uber.com/blog/h3>

TABLE 2. An overview of some indicative works for activities detected in vessel mobility data, along with the main processing method used for each one. The selected activities presented are loitering, fishing (including trawling or longlining) and Search-and-Rescue operations (SAR). The mentioned events are also considered in a rule-based Event Calculus approach in [327] and (two of them) in [329].

Activity	Work	Method(s) Utilized	Year
Loitering	[330]	Threshold-based filtering	2016
	[331]	Leader algorithm & statistics	2017
	[332]	Generalized Additive Models	2018
	[333]	Multi-scale sliding windows & CNNs	2022
	[334]	Isolation Forest	2023
Fishing	[335]	Random Forests	2017
	[336]	Kernel Density Estimation	2019
	[337]	Convolutional Neural Networks	2020
	[338]	Bi-LSTMs	2020
	[339]	Random Forests	2020
	[340]	Random Forests / Support Vector Machines / Logistic Regression	2021
	[341]	VGG16 / InceptionV3 / NASNetLarge / DenseNet201	2021
	[342]	Convolutional Auto-encoders	2021
	[343]	VGG16	2021
	[344]	RNNs, LSTMs, CNNs	2023
	[345]	Logistic Regression	2023
SAR	[346]	Random Forests	2018
	[347]	DBSCAN	2018
	[348]	GENDIS & Logistic Regression	2019
	[349]	Decision Trees / Random Forests / Gradient Boosted Trees	2021

have translated the loitering issue into a specified anomaly detection problem [41], [350]. For example, the authors of [330] employ an event processing mechanism to filter irregularly slow speeds for extended periods of time, generating loitering alerts. [331] first partitions the positional data into zones, using the Leader algorithm, and then soft computing relationships are explored for merging. A loitering instance can be identified, using statistics on the vessel's stay in each zone. [333] introduces a redundancy feature on the trajectories extracted through multi-scale sliding windows, isolating loitering events based on a corresponding threshold. A convolutional neural network (CNN) is applied on each loitering segment, identifying four typical shapes of such behavior (disordered retracting, lasso, regular reciprocating and random coil shape). Furthermore, [334] calculates a loitering score, based on spatio-temporal characteristics like the frequency of extreme turns and the difference of vessel heading and course, with an Isolation Forest algorithm employed to extract the appropriate parameters. Loitering can also assist in detecting possible Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated (IUU) fishing activity [231]. In [332], the AIS trajectories are split into smaller segments and Generalized Additive Models are utilized to determine normal behavior in each location of an overall grid of the area of interest. The indicators selected for this study are average speed, time spend and distance traveled in each area. Then, for each input record a probability of an observed value for the three loitering indicators can be calculated. The frequency of loitering behavior is then used to identify hotspots for fishing

activities; with a case study at the Indonesian Exclusive Economic Zone.

The modeling of fishing patterns has been the focus of several published works [39], [351]. In [327] fishing, and more specifically trawling, is considered the movement of steady speed, initiated with a heading change within a (predefined) fishing area. The speed-related thresholds are from 1 to 9 knots. Similarly, suspicious slow moving activity in protected areas are considered as possible illegal fishing in [329]. Large AIS dataset of fishing vessels give the opportunity for advanced DM techniques to be exploited. In [336] KDE-based clustering is performed upon the full trajectories between the same stop points, resulting in a global anomaly score by calculating the distance to the center of the cluster it belongs. A second (local) anomaly score is calculated based on the percentage each vessel remains dark (does not transmit its positions) during the trips. Combining these scores for each vessel give a notion for possible illegal fishing activities on each new trip. Supervised learning on labeled mobility data, by domain experts, is employed in [337], where the authors use a CNN to classify the activity from scaled and segmented trajectories. Focusing on the system's performance, random forests are incorporated in a distributed fast framework (i.e. Akka) upon continuous data streams in [339], resulting in sub-second latency. RNNs, like LSTM's and Bi-LSTMs, are used in [338] and [344] working on the areas around Taiwan and Norway respectively, with the latter also providing a solution for accurately labeling trajectory data. O'Farrell et al. [335] note that the method point based labels can be effective in long-set fisheries, like pelagic longlining, but a window-based approach is more suitable for the short-set instances. Similarly in [345], the authors propose a dynamic windowing system, based on points of interest, to find candidate sub-trajectories, and then passes them into a Logistic Regression model for the behavior detection. The difficulty of annotating large datasets for efficient learning algorithms is also touched on in [342], where semi-supervised methods (Convolutional auto-encoders) model different types of vessel behaviors, including two types of fishing activity. The proposed framework follows the computer vision path of [340] and [341], where the input vessel trajectories are first translated into images and then get fed to a trained model that provides the fishing activity recognition. The selected classifiers were Random Forests, Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression for [340] and deep learning algorithms VGG16, InceptionV3, NASNetLarge, and DenseNet201 for [341]. Positional data have also been exploited to determine the specific fishing type of the vessels. The operation type of China's offshore boats is determined by feeding the trajectory data into a CNN (a VGG16 to be precise) in [343], allowing for monitoring possible changes in their fishing methods. Another interesting application is the identification of fishing gear aboard the vessels [352].

In SAR operations detection the vessels attempt to provide aid in dangerous situations at sea in a timely manner.

Several solutions have been proposed for determining the need for a SAR operation [353], [354], [355], creating an emergency response plan [356] or assisting with autonomous technologies [357]. For the detection of SAR activity on trajectories, an Event Calculus approach uses abrupt changes in speed and heading of SAR vessels for periods over 1 hour to determine the appropriate intervals [327]. Even though there are vessels operating explicitly for SAR missions, with a declared vessel type, their trips might include traveling between ports and harbors for maintenance purposes. Furthermore, there exist instances where other types of vessels participate in such missions as well [346]. An experimental comparison of different ML techniques (Decision Trees, Random Forests and Gradient Boosted Trees) for classifying AIS trajectories [349] has showcased their accuracy. Vessel speed and the trip's duration are identified as the most important features for these classifiers. The approach proposed in [347] focuses on significant changes of the vessel's course (turns over 40 degrees), with incremental clustering identifying areas with possible SAR movement. Different types of SAR maneuvers are identified in [348] where a classifier is trained on synthetic data and is applied on real AIS trajectories, building on shapelet transformation [358].

VI. PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS

Moving to predictive analytics, many works are tasked to provide accurate forecasts regarding the future movement of the vessels (see Table 3). This ranges from generating a route forecast for the short or long term and routing based on the projected weather conditions upon the vessel's path, to accurate estimations of its next destination and the moment of its arrival.

A. ROUTE FORECASTING

One of the most significant tasks in maritime mobility analytics is obtaining accurate forecasts of vessel paths. Traditional vessel movement predictions primarily rely on kinematic equations, while data-driven approaches rely on AIS data to extract historical routes and knowledge [32]. Grid-based approaches leverage historical data to extract mobility graphs for their forecasts. For example, in [359] clustering is used to extract areas of common movement and generate a graph, that can provide forecasts until the vessel's destination. On a route suggestion solution, [360] utilizes Delaunay triangulation bathymetric data to create a graph and produce fuel cost-efficient paths from dynamic programming. In a relevant approach, partitioning sea at a grid, [361] employs an multivariate K-order Markov chain method to extract a possible future path as a series of grid cells. Extracted routes from historical data can also be utilized. More precisely, classification techniques, like support vector machines, are used in [362] to assign the most probable route, based on the current trajectory. Murray et al. [363] proposed a solution that also uses classification, along

with a two-step clustering process. During execution, each vessel trip is classified into a group of past trajectories, based on its recent positions. The forecasted route is generated considering only the behavior of the trajectories that fall to the same class.

A plethora of methods for vessel route forecasting are based on different NN architectures, especially in the past few years, since the trajectories can be considered as time-series [32]. In a significant portion, the memory capabilities of recurrent neural networks (RNNs) are exploited to incorporate the last recorded locations of the vessels. As an example, [364] uses the Long-short Term Memory (LSTM) architecture for forecasts 60 minutes into the future, receiving multiple past positions as input. An encoder-decoder schema is proposed in [365] where both simple and bidirectional LSTMs (Bi-LSTMs) are employed. When encoding the input, the past few positions of the vessel are fed into a Bi-LSTM network and then through an attention mechanism, creating a context vector. The next step, decoding, produces the forecasts using a combination of LSTMs and Multi Layer Perceptrons. The resulting forecasts are provided with fixed temporal distance between them, reaching up to three hours. Moreover, in the extended work [366], the proposed schema is enhanced with Bayesian deep learning, that considers the prediction uncertainty in its results. For a more lightweight approach, Suo et al. in [367] selected another recurrent neural network architecture, namely the Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). Dedicated experiments comparing the proposed solution to LSTM were conducted, highlighting its computational efficiency while maintaining its accuracy.

B. DESTINATION PREDICTION

The destination port for a vessel's trip is included in the AIS messages. However, as a manually inserted field, its accuracy is often lacking. The user input is often incorrectly spelled, left unchanged from a previous trip, or refer to multiple ports in passenger vessel trips. The similarity of the current vessel trajectory and past tracks, together with port traffic can be exploited to determine the destination [368]. Eljabu et al. have proposed a methodology that first transforms the input trajectory (through segmentation and interpolation), and then uses different similarity measures to return the most probable destination [369]. Gouareb et al. on the other hand, transform the moving space (trajectories and ports) into a graph and then use an ML technique to provide prediction upon these graphs [370]. The location data are transformed into an encoded sequence and a sequence-to-sequence architecture is utilized in Nguyen et al., to determine the possible future path of the vessel including the end port [371].

C. ESTIMATED TIME OF ARRIVAL

A critical part of shipping is accurate scheduling, due to the scarcity of available berths at ports. The results of path-finding algorithms may be exploited and expanded to extract an estimated time of arrival (ETA) of vessels [372].

Noting that a vessel's speed is directly affected by the current weather conditions, Ogura et al. address this issue by incorporating the wave height and period, the wind speed and the direction of the ship's bow to first determine a probable path and then use distribution of similar vessels to determine the average moving speed, and hence the final ETA [373]. Alternatively, the ETA without path predictions can be achieved by exploiting statistics from historical data. Kolley et al. follow this approach by translating the problem as regression and apply a series of statistical and ML models on AIS-based records [374]. Using a feature set that includes the distance to the destination port, the speed and difference between heading and course (drift), together with the vessels' dimensions, the k-nearest-neighbours algorithm and the NNs seem to outperform the other models. An indicator whether the vessel is currently in open waters or not is also considered by the network. Similarly, the positional and movement features of AIS and LRIT data are used in an experimental comparison of different NNs, including RNNs, by El Mekkaoui et al. [375], that showcased the performance of such architectures. Several weather features, such as the wind intensity and direction and water level, are also fed into a multi-layered NN in Jahn et al [376]. Recently, Zhang et al. has included booking information of a predicted pilotage area for the vessel, to generate an ETA based on a temporal convolutional neural network [377].

D. WEATHER ROUTING

Besides extracting an accurate prediction, providing a recommendation on the optimal path for a vessel considering its dynamic environment is also another major task [378]. Safety concerns, fuel consumption and emissions are main aspects of the trips to be optimized [379], [380], other than the arrival time. A major factor affecting a vessel's path is the forecasted weather conditions during its trip [226], including but not limited to the wind, waves, currents and swells, together with some extreme weather phenomena. Commonly found approaches include the modified isochrone method and dynamic programming [42]. The isochrone method generates all possible points that can be reached by a vessel according to the weather conditions and has been adapted extensively [381], [382], while dynamic programming algorithms [383] break-down the problem, solving only parts of it at a time.

From a DM perspective, the weather conditions can be incorporated from AIS-dataset extracted mobility graphs and use modified path-finding algorithms to produce effective routes that [384], [385], [386]. For example, [387] introduces a modified Dijkstra algorithm to compute optimal vessel routes, with regards to CO_2 emissions. The framework is suitable for both motor-operated vessels and sailboats, considering the intensity as well as the direction of the weather features, and is implemented in Python. Moreover, the capabilities NNs have been exploited to estimate the fuel consumption for possible routes [388], often considering the engine specifications as well [42].

TABLE 3. Major works for predictive analytics on vessel movement, including route forecasting, destination prediction, arrival time estimation (ETA) and weather routing, with the main methods they utilize and the

Task	Work	Method(s) Utilized	Year
Route Forecasting	[362]	Support Vector Machine	2016
	[361]	K-order Markov Chain	2019
	[367]	GRU	2020
	[359]	Shortest path	2021
	[365]	Bi-LSTM & attention mechanism	2021
	[363]	Karhunen-Loève transform Gaussian Mixture Mode	2022
Destination Prediction	[366]	Bi-LSTM & attention mechanism Bayesian Neural Networks	2022
	[371]	seq2seq (LSTM / GRU)	2018
	[368]	Random Forest	2020
	[369]	Linear interpolation & Similarity Measurements	2021
ETA	[370]	kNN (upon heterogenous graph)	2022
	[372]	Dijkstra	2018
	[376]	Multi-layer NN	2018
	[375]	FFNNs / RNN / LSTM / GRU	2020
	[373]	Bayesian learning (upon speed)	2021
	[374]	Linear Regression / Neural Network Decision Tree Regressor / kNN	2023
	[386]	Probabilistic Roadmap & Dijkstra	2023
[377]	Temporal Convolutional Network	2024	
Weather Routing	[383]	3D Dynamic programming	2012
	[381]	Modified Isochrones method	2013
	[384]	Dijkstra	2016
	[388]	Dijkstra & Multi-layer NN	2020
	[379]	Spline-LSTM & Dijkstra	2022
	[226]	Lagrange interpolation & Nearest Neighbor	2022
	[385]	A* algorithm	2022
	[387]	Dijkstra	2023
	[382]	Modified Isochrones method variations	2024

VII. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

As described, several approaches have been proposed for the different data mining tasks regarding vessel traffic. Although all these approaches have proven to model vessel movement accurately, few challenges and open issues can be identified. In this section, we provide a list of the most prominent issues that arise with processing vessel trajectory data, indicating possible directions for future works.

A. MULTI-PURPOSE FRAMEWORKS

Along the many approaches found for vessel trajectory DM, most works tend to focus on achieving high accuracy for a specific single goal and do not present a compact interpretation of vessel activity. For instance, identifying anomalous or irregular activities at sea has been achieved by modeling normal vessel behavior [28]. Most frequently though, these models cannot be used to provide an estimation for future vessel paths or detect the specific activities the vessels take part in.

B. BLACK-BOX APPROACHES

Additionally, the recent developments on neural networks (NNs) have led to a significant spike of such approaches for tasks like forecasting and reconstructing vessel trajectories [32]. Even though these approaches have proven to be highly effective, a few disadvantages should be noted.

First, due to the nature of NNs, the resulting models are often treated as black boxes, as they are not easily interpreted by the user [27]. This proves to be a significant obstacle in exploiting their capabilities in critical scenarios with real-world stakes, as stakeholders cannot trust their results without entirely understanding their reasoning process. For use cases such as autonomous technologies and decision systems, post-processing or advanced XAI mechanisms are required to achieve transparency in the resulting models. In general, creating robust and descriptive models allows for more generalizable and acceptable results.

C. ADDRESSING DATA SCARCITY

NN-based frameworks usually require large trajectory datasets for training, in order to be achieve the desired accuracy. This fact does not allow such solutions to be easily utilized in instances with few historical samples available, either due to the scarcity of the data (for example in trips far from the coasts) or due to the infrequent trips for specific itineraries. The lack of significant historical data is also present when dealing with extreme environmental parameters. For example, instances of vessels traveling with harsh weather conditions are rare compared to normal movement. The transferability of the models is no simple manner, with the inability to train on smaller datasets being a major issue. Additionally, this data scarcity issue becomes an significant obstacle when trends and recent behavior is noticeably different than the past. On such occasions, incorporating recent movement patterns should be addressed through different context-aware architectures [27], [389]. The techniques of self-supervised learning can also be employed in order to augment the training datasets, especially in application scenarios lacking labeled data, with relatively few works relying on them so far [390], [391].

D. EXTRACTING ENRICHED ROUTES

As presented, vessel traffic can also be described by extracting commonly followed routes, since their movement is not confined into a road network as in land vehicles [43]. While several approaches exist for this purpose, most provide universal shipping lanes, that do not offer insights regarding specific types of vessels or activities. Fishing boats, for example, tend to follow different paths compared to commercial tankers. As a result, the identified routes cannot be easily incorporated into specific use cases and applications, as the provided averages may not be appropriately selected. In general, there is a need for a systematic analysis of the large amounts of vessel trajectories, in order to model their mobility patterns in an interpretable way.

E. LONG-TERM ROUTE FORECASTING

Most works on route forecasting focus on a short-term temporal horizon, typically from a few minutes up to 1-hour. Even though this is crucial for applications like collision avoidance and arrival time estimation from smaller trips,

the vast majority of commercial vessels take part in much longer voyages, sometimes lasting more than a week [318]. A notable exception was presented in [392], where Particle Filtering (PF) is employed, with some of forecasts extending up to 60 hours into the future, but with errors around 50 km for those long trips and with the performance burden of the PF required. In another example, the Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process has been utilized for trips up until 40 hours in duration [393], [394]. For a full picture of the future vessel movement, the forecasts should include positions up until the (reported) destination of the vessel, regardless of the trip's duration and length.

F. SEQUENCE-TO-SEQUENCE MODELS

The efficiency of sequence-to-sequence models for modeling longer trips has been showcased in recent works [365], [366]. Due to their nature, these models require a large portion of the past vessel movement, in order to extract an accurate prediction. This, in turn, would present as a new obstacle in integrating such approaches in real-time monitoring systems, as a dedicated infrastructure should be responsible for collecting, transforming and storing these past tracks at all times, for a forecast to be available. The range of AIS receivers is limited to a few km in most cases, and this assuming no large obstacles (like mountains) would be present between them and the target vessel. As a result, on-board solutions that use such sequence-to-sequence models may not be feasible. This would become even more apparent when dealing with smaller vessels of limited capacity to hold long-range sensors but highly rely on data-driven situational awareness for safe traveling, like autonomous vessels [13], [185].

G. INFORMATION FUSION

Few works consider the characteristics of the vessels or the voyage in question in their algorithms, providing common results for all queries. Incorporating query-specific features is a crucial component for tasks like trip prediction or anomaly detection. Features like the age of the vessel or its provided desired time of arrival may be useful when dealing with traffic congestion or weather conditions [42]. Moreover, the vessel characteristics could be useful for determining which route is more likely to follow. For example, larger vessels prefer routes that are not close to the coast or shallow passages, to avoid possible groundings, while smaller ones do not face such an issue. Finally, repetitive trips, especially in passenger vessels, can be fully described solely based on the departure time or day for some instances.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The continuous generation of large mobility datasets from hundreds of thousands of vessels operating all over the globe provide an opportunity for advanced analytics through data mining. In this work, we offer a detailed review on mobility data analytics upon vessel trajectories. First, the motivation, the major concepts and the challenges of data mining are

presented. After contextualizing vessel trajectory analytics as a subcategory of spatio-temporal data mining, we list the significant stakeholders of the shipping industry, mention the different types of data sources and describe the essential steps for dataset preparation. Moreover, we present the major mining tasks for maritime trajectories, categorized primarily as descriptive and predictive analytics. The main purpose of each task is described along indicative approaches found in recent literature; we provide examples for both traditional and machine learning processing frameworks. Finally, we recap some of the most important challenges found in the aforementioned works, providing some directions for future research efforts on this domain.

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